

ReNEW

D3.1 Framework Architecture & core infrastructure components

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance of Internet Of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
BDIS	Big Data Infrastructural Services
BPMN	Business Process Modelling Notation
CI	Critical Infrastructure
DT	Digital Twin
DUET	Digital Urban European Twins
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standard Institute
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICS	Institute for Corporate Security Studies
IDS	International Data Spaces
IT	Information Technology
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KG	Knowledge Graph
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDES	Linked Data Event Stream
LL	Living Lab
ODT	Open Digital Twin
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SDP	Smart Data Platform
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality

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1. Introduction

1.1. Summary

As climate change severely affects the performance of IWT (Inland Waterway Transport) operation, the priority is to create and test new solutions for both climate-neutral and climate-resilient IWT. Even when the focus is on improving infrastructure resilience, a climate resilient IWT can only be realized by looking at the entire IWT system.

The **ReNEW** project wants to establish new ways of improving IWT resilience by:

- Continued digital transformation of the IWT sector, improved interaction between infrastructure management systems and barge operations (for instance to allow autonomous barge operation),
- Creating insight into the adverse effects of predictable and unexpected events (drought, extreme weather events, accidents) to allow a shorter response time and increased resilience.

Data Spaces and Digital Twins (DTs) have achieved prominence in recent years across different domains (e.g., Industry 4.0, Smart Manufacturing, Intelligent Transport and Smart Cities). DTs are employed for predicting outcomes and assessing “what-if” scenarios. This leads to improved capabilities in terms of process monitoring, processes optimization, predictive management and decision making.

The **ReNEW** project aims to, amongst others, capture different hydrological river (sub)systems in so-called “local digital twins”. This requires the integration of multiple data sources provided by several parties as well as the composition of several algorithms to model the behaviour of the system. This in turn raises the question of how to discover, understand, trust and integrate data sources and algorithms into one system. It is exactly these challenges that are addressed by dataspace.

This deliverable focuses on the specification of a reference architecture that maps the local digital twin components onto a dataspace architecture, explaining the benefits this has in the context of the **ReNEW** project.

1.2. In this document

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. In chapter 2 we discuss the conceptual architecture of local digital twins and the benefits they can bring for modelling inland waterway systems. We discuss the major concepts and list the key components and their responsibilities.

In chapter 3 we explain what dataspace are and why they are useful for building digital twins, more specifically the ones we consider in the **ReNEW** project. We specifically address how useful they are in bringing data and models together and enabling trustworthy decision support.

In chapter 4, we present a new reference architecture that combines the architectural patterns of the local digital twins and data spaces by mapping digital twin components onto a dataspace reference architecture.

We conclude in chapter 5 by discussing the highlights of the document. The appendix contains a backlog with high-level user stories related to the Living Labs that serve as a foundation for the future roadmap.

1.3. Compliance table

This deliverable lives in the scope of Work Package 3: European IWT Data Space and Digital Twin solutions for Resilience and Sustainability. It relates to the tasks of this work package as follows:

	Task description		Applicability for this Deliverable
T 3.1	Green Resilient IWT Dataspace and generic Digital Twin architecture		
ST 3.1.1	Architecture based on Living Labs and Technical backlog definition (IMEC)	IN SCOPE	We propose a generic architecture that matches the goals
ST 3.1.2	Living Labs Services Adaptations	NOT IN SCOPE	This is left for the second version of this deliverable.
T 3.2	Green Resilient Dataspace components, solutions and tools		
ST 3.2.1	Green Resilient IWT Dataspace components, solutions, and tools	IN SCOPE	We explain the proven foundations of our architecture, pointing to the state of the art in Digital Twins and Data Spaces
ST 3.2.2	Data integration and data space sharing components and connectors, solution Accelerators	IN SCOPE	We propose building blocks for the generic digital twin architecture in a dataspace context, including core digital twin components, dataspace connectors and robust/efficient data transfer building blocks relying on open standards for interoperability. Combining these building blocks will result in said solution accelerator.
ST 3.2.3	Library of Data Connectors	IN SCOPE	We propose a generic approach for connecting data and algorithms to the digital twin. We revisit this topic in the next iteration when the Living Labs scope allows us to be more concrete.
T 3.3	Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic Application		
ST 3.3.1	Digital Twins for Decision Making, Metrics and KPIs evaluation	IN SCOPE	De proposed architecture provides the foundations for decision making and points to challenges in this domain regarding the need for smart data. We revisit this topic in the next iteration when the Living Labs scope allows us to be more concrete.
ST 3.3.2	Libraries and Tools for DT enabled dynamic simulation models	IN SCOPE	The proposed architecture suggests a proven method for generalizing (simulation) model integration in the digital twin. We revisit this topic in the next iteration when the Living Labs scope allows us to be more concrete.
T 3.4	Generic Applications Deployment to the Living labs		
ST 3.4.1	Living Labs Resilience & Sustainability services and applications	NOT IN SCOPE	
ST 3.4.2	Autonomous Barge system Digital Twin	NOT IN SCOPE	
ST 3.4.3	Deployment to the LLs	NOT IN SCOPE	

2. Digital Twins

2.1. Introduction

Digital twins are virtual replicas of physical objects or systems that can be used for simulation, analysis, and control. Although the idea of digital twins originated decades ago, the first actual digital twin concepts were introduced in the 2000s in the field of manufacturing. Digital twins are an important part of Industry 4.0 and typically model closed systems that can be designed to mathematical precision. Closed system digital twins typically model specific industrial systems, such as manufacturing processes or supply chains. These digital twins are designed to optimize individual components within a specific system, rather than taking into account the complex interconnections and interactions between different systems and factors.

On the other hand, Local digital twins as defined by living-in.eu [1], are digital representations of complex systems, such as urban environments, transport systems and ecosystems, that model the physical, social, and economic factors and interactions between them that make up that system. They provide a comprehensive view of a geographical area's infrastructure, resources, and behaviours, and can be used to simulate various scenarios and make data-supported decisions to improve geographic planning and management.

Consequently, the key difference between local and closed system digital twins lies in their scope and purpose. Local digital twins model the entirety of a geographic environment and its many components, whereas closed system digital twins focus on optimizing specific industrial processes or systems. For the purpose of the ReNEW project, we will focus on Local Digital Twins.

2.2. Open Local Digital Twins

2.2.1. Open digital twin Design

The architecture of a digital twin system does not have a fixed structure, as it is a combination of various information technology capabilities. To implement digital twins on a large scale, such as on a national level, an open digital twin framework is necessary. Several national digital twin initiatives, such as those in the United Kingdom, Luxemburg, Sweden, and the Netherlands, have similar visions for digital twin architecture and have established main principles for their implementation. The Centre for Digital Built Britain has outlined the GEMINI principles to guide the development of a National Digital Twin, and these principles are being applied in the ReNEW project with its functional and technical capabilities.

Purpose Must have clear purpose	Public good Must be used to deliver genuine public benefit in perpetuity	Value creation Must enable value creation and performance improvement	Insight Must provide determinable insight into the built environment
Trust Must be trustworthy	Security Must enable security and secure itself	Openness Must be as open As possible	Quality Must be built on data of appropriate quality
Function Must function effectively	Federation Must be based on a standard connected environment	Curation Must have clear ownership, governance and regulation	Evolution Must be able to adapt as society and technology evolve

Figure 1: The Centre for Digital Built Britain (CDBB) has summarised in the GEMINI principles, which are a group of values set out by the Centre for Digital Built Britain to aid the development of a National Digital Twin.

For the ReNEW digital twin, we explicitly mention the following GEMINI Principles as important to realize within the architecture:

- **Public good:** the protection against – or evaluation of – various cascading effects caused by specific events assists to protect the public benefits, and creates immediate value for public stakeholder by increasing resilience and sustainability
- **Value Creation:** the value of being able to assess dependencies and their interrelationships and the possible mitigation scenarios, will enable the stakeholders to reduce societal damage as well as economic damage. It will equally allow for effective risk management at

asset, process, and system levels.

- **Insight:** it is obvious that the digital twin architecture needs to support better collection of insights in management of the IWT environment.
- **Security:** ReNEW is potentially handling sensitive data on IWT related topics, such as positional data of ships via AIS messages and planning data of logistic terminals. The first one is considered pseudo-personal data as skippers often live on their vessel, the latter can leak commercial details with regard to how a supply chain performs and is set up. Thus the architecture needs to address the secure sharing of this data from the beginning, by design.
- **Openness:** The digital twin architecture can bring forward collaborative models, open standards, ... to prevent bilateral and once-only integrations of the different major components like data management, simulation models, ...
- **Quality:** The different assets that are used to model event impact, being data or compute, need to be tracked within digital twin scenarios for their quality attributes. This is a call for asset governance and management, data and model signatures. Quality needs to be traceable over chains of assets being used, as we know that quality will not always be easy to quantify in all interpretations (e.g., limits of AI).
- **Federation:** respecting a federated system from the beginning is very important for a digital twin architecture. A federated system is a group of components (e.g., databases) that share information with each other, but remain independent entities. Multiple such entities are combined to share and to access data, while maintaining control over their own data and operations. It's like a cooperative network where data is distributed and managed collectively, but each participant retains autonomy over their own data. It is also the key requirement of data spaces. But federation requires common practices and standards to be effective. A digital twin architecture can bring capabilities and agreements to make this work.
- **Curation:** in ReNEW, the digital twin framework can induce better governance within the usage of data and compute in the different living labs.

2.2.2. Local digital twin ambition levels

Digital twins and frameworks come in different flavours and can be classified in terms of their capabilities (see **Figure 2**). In ReNEW, we are aiming for level 4 to be able to simulate effects on resilience and impact on the environment caused by certain events or choices, to make an evidence-based decision between multiple options. This means that static and dynamic data is needed, but also simulation models to see the impact of "What-If" analysis. ReNEW should also pave the way to allow for research in the future on bi-directional support from the virtual twin to the physical twin, which will allow automation of e.g., operational actions in the full supply chain of IWT. Of course,

throughout various living labs other levels (e.g., level 0 to level 3) digital twin systems might be built if the use cases demand for such implementations.

Figure 2: Digital twin ambition levels are defined in terms of the system’s capabilities.

For a comprehensive overview of the different Digital Twin Capability groups (see **Figure 3**) and the digital twin capabilities, we refer to **Appendix I**.

Figure 3: Digital twin capability groups [3] as identified by the Digital Twin Consortium.

2.2.3. Getting data to the digital twin

Getting data to the digital twin involves addressing many of the Data Services capabilities such as data acquisition & ingestion, data streaming and data transformation. But it also covers capabilities like meta data management and data storage services. We discuss the capabilities that we consider the most important in ReNEW context below.

Data ingestion

Provided that data sources are available, the challenge of accessing and using the data remains to be addressed. The following scenarios may occur:

- 1) The data provider is a third party and the data is a static dataset:
Depending on the situation, the data may be consumed when it is needed or it can be onboarded into a storage service (see below) and transformed (see below) to a suitable standard format if needed.
- 2) The data provider is a third party publishing a dynamic data set (e.g., sensor data):
It is possible to consume the publisher service directly from the DT but this strategy hinges on many assumptions such as sufficient availability and limited latency. In many other cases, it is a good idea to replicate the data somewhere close to where it is needed and in a ready-to-use format. This can be done with LDES [7], [9] technology (see section 2.5.2) or other suitable technologies depending on the publisher's capabilities related to both linked data and event streaming.
- 3) The data provider is publishing a dynamic data set and is part of the DT ecosystem:

In this case, it is recommended to converge to LDES data publishing and consumption to ensure maximal performance and availability. See section 2.5.2 for more information on Linked Data Event Streams.

Data storage

It is always possible to use data directly from the data publisher's services. However, digital twins are often quite discriminating when it comes to data formats, data availability and latency. This is why a more robust approach involves replicating data in proximity of the point of use. This can be close to the simulation models that ingest the data and/or close to the point where the data needs to be visualized.

Depending on the needs one can make use of appropriate services that can be easily deployed (e.g., using Docker). The LDES standard can be used for replicating data to this service as well if deemed required.

Data processing and transformation

Often data needs to be processed before it can be used. Such processing can involve filtering, transformation, aggregation, anonymization, calibration, etc. If not offered by the data publisher as separate data streams, such capabilities can be incorporated into LDES pipelines.

Metadata management (including Ontology Management and Model repositories)

Users of the Digital Twin need the ability to discover, save and reuse data sets, simulation/AI models and other assets from within a digital twin environment. This calls for asset management infrastructure.

2.2.4. Data & Asset Discoverability

Regardless of its ambition level, the value of digital twins is determined by the data and the algorithms connected to it. Especially in open digital twins, the ability to find and connect data and algorithms is crucial. As such, a digital twin must have the possibility to discover data and algorithms that have been made available. This is one of the areas where digital twins should benefit from dataspace that offer built-in data and asset discoverability.

Digital twins should present their users with ways of connecting to the Dataspace marketplace, find and select data sources, algorithms or other assets and use them for their digital twin use cases.

The conceptual mechanisms for data discovery in dataspace are discussed in chapter 3.

2.2.5. Digital Twin Cases & Scenarios

Users working with the digital twin will probably need to keep track of the context in which they are using it. Cases and scenarios as introduced by DUET [4][5][6] offer this context.

A good example is a case where a model is used to compare the logistics flows using barges on a river in a business-as-usual scenario, with the hypothetical logistics flows in case infrastructure (changes) and policies are implemented. A simulation model can be used to assess the impact of the implemented measures. An example of such an approach can be found in the Physical Internet Living Labs project (PILL) in Flanders [10]. Different scenarios allow us to compare the predicted effects of different measures to the business-as-usual and to each other.

Aside from some descriptive information, a scenario typically describes which data sources and algorithms are used and how they are connected. This enables the digital twin orchestrator to control the data flow inside a simulation/prediction run. This is conceptually depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: This figure shows how a digital twin case and scenario can refer to data sources and algorithms. By describing how algorithms are connected to input and output data sources, one can also describe the end-2-end dataflow in a digital twin scenario.

Any digital twin that is used to create policy should have an elaborate Case & Scenario management that allows to fully document, trace and reproduce experiments.

2.2.6. Resilient data pipelines: Connecting models to the data

The connections between algorithms and data sources that are described by a digital twin scenario in fact represent an acyclic directed graph (ADG). ADGs are typically used to describe data processing pipelines. The figure below shows how this could materialize in practice in a digital twin. The example used is a typical one: using both live and historical data for traffic and air quality to make predictions based on actual data.

Figure 5: a classic case for a digital twin for predicting traffic and air quality based on historic and actual data.

There are two main challenges in creating such pipelines:

- Using and combining algorithms and data sources interchangeably.
- Organizing the data flow in a robust way that can recover from disruptions and that ensures properly responsive twins.

The challenge of **combining algorithms and data** interchangeably requires efforts in interoperability. A common interface for algorithms can be defined in terms of (i) the data sources being fully descriptive about their format, their schema and their semantics and (ii) the models being fully descriptive about the supported connection protocols, supported data formats, schemas and semantics.

The challenge of setting up **resilient data pipelines** that ensure that the data is close to the model whenever required is not a straightforward one. We introduce LDES (linked Data Event Streams) in chapter 3. In short, LDES offers a robust way of replicating data by allowing to get in sync and stay in sync with the data source. It also balances the efforts for scalable data publishing between the data publisher and the data consumer in order to build more scalable systems.

2.2.7. Visualization and analytics

When people think of digital twins, they often imagine all kinds of visualizations in 3D that replicate the behaviour of real-world objects. These visualizations are typically aimed at a broad audience, experts and non-experts to give more insight of what is going on. In open, local digital twins, this means 3D maps and 2D maps of an environment. By zooming in or out, a situation or the outcome of an experiment can be made more comprehensible.

Besides map-based visualization, another way of looking at the data is graphs and tables. They typically serve a more technically adept audience like subject matter experts and data scientists. Typically, analytical environments such as BI (business intelligence) platforms, notebooks, etc. are used for this purpose.

2.3. Resilient & Cognitive Digital Twins

The architecture needs to be able to support resilient digital twins, as introduced in the paper referenced in [2]. That paper states: *"the digital counterpart should help to make decisions either manually or fully automatically. However, the digital twin should be resilient and not make bad decisions when confronted with completely new situations. Answers to 'what-if analyses' need to be compared and interpreted"*.

The digital twin architecture that we propose in ReNEW aligns with this vision of the need for a resilient digital twin described in above mentioned paper, and the goal of building a DTO, a digital twin of an organization. In our case this means the living labs and their different use cases to enable resilient & green IWT.

Cognitive digital twins touch on the same goals, as they aim to combine data and technological resources and engines to allow better cognitive reasoning on complex problems. The following figure taken from the aforementioned paper [2] sketches the same goals. The idea is to bridge human cognition capabilities with digital assets to be able to address better resilience (e.g., in production environments, but in ReNEW to make better, more eco-friendly, or apt choices in the logistics supply chain). Cognitive digital twins will add tools to assist this.

Figure 6: Resilient digital twins (figure taken from [2])

2.4. Smart Data

Given that data for data-informed decision making at societal scale calls for minimal data bias and maximum understanding and transparency, how can these goals be achieved? The solution lies in using (big volumes of) managed data i.e., smart data: data which is produced at scale and that is ready for decision-making. Smart data is the result of transforming raw data by applying the FAIR principles (i.e., findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), making it fit for purpose (e.g., addressing bias in decision-making, transforming it into efficient processable formats, ...), and governing the processes used along the way as illustrated in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7: Smart data focuses on essential process steps, taken from [14]

The first step within the smart data generation process is to understand the domain challenges (which can be societal or business) and the associated use cases. The real goal for smart data in the

context of better decision-making is to enable actionable insights that can be used in a specific (or multiple) domain(s). A thorough knowledge of the reasons for using the data (e.g., identifying applications which will use the data) within a particular domain is the basis for determining the correct next steps in creating smart data from large quantities of raw data. Expressing these domain challenges in a standardized way (e.g., TOGAF or BMM-models) is crucial to enable the broad (re)-use of datasets at a societal scale.

A checklist of smart data properties can be a useful tool when addressing domain challenges in decision-making (whether on an operational or policy level). Such a checklist is given below, however, should not be considered exhaustive nor a hard requirement to meet all criteria. This list classifies properties to keep in mind when reviewing the usefulness of datasets, such as Trusted, Contextual, Relevant, Cognitive, Predictive and Consumable.

ATTRIBUTE	DESCRIPTION
Trusted	To be able to take decisions on insights obtained from data, having trust in the quality, consistency, accuracy, origin, protection and security, etc. of that data is crucial. A defined level of trust is needed to enable accountability for the actions that are taken based on the data.
Contextual	The context of data is an important part of the metadata of a data collection. It gives information about the collection of the data (e.g., location, time, measurement conditions, etc.); the use of the data (usage policies, key interpretation guidelines, constraints, limitations, etc.); the managed meaning of the data and much more. The context of the data should be sufficiently complete to address, as far as possible, the full range of use cases. The more domains that the data can address, the more context will be needed. Notice that different contexts of data could point to each other, e.g., using semantic web linked data techniques. Data provenance (i.e., records about the trail of the data) is also part of the context and is key to enabling trust.
Relevant	Even when data are trusted and contextual, they are not necessarily directly usable or relevant for the targeted use cases. It is important to organize the data from different sources in such a way that applications can easily find them, and that the data are published and presented in such a way that they are directly relevant to the applications. For that, data needs to be curated.
Cognitive	In many cases, raw data needs to be processed to make it more understandable, especially when it is unstructured e.g., streaming media, images, etc. Cognitive computing refers to technology such as machine learning, machine reasoning, natural language processing, speech recognition, and human-computer interaction that transforms data into more usable forms for economic or decision-making purposes.
Predictive	In the process of transforming raw data into data that provides insights to drive certain decisions, it is important to focus on trends and predictions. For example, in digital twins it is important to be able to make predictions about the evolution of certain data sets such as flood risks or the impact of certain actions, and to go back and forth in time. Smart data should be tailored and presented in such a way that prediction is facilitated, e.g., by adding enough context of certain causes of trend changes in the data and allowing for 'time travel'.
Consumable	Data needs to be presented so that it can be easily used by humans and machines. Thus, it is very important to design the access, presentation and service layers (e.g., API) so they are appropriately tuned to the usage that will be made of the data. To make data consumable, the needs of the decision makers and their tools (e.g., digital twins) need to be well understood and targeted.

Figure 8: Target data attributes when applying smart data operations, taken from [14]

The overarching process is described by Gartner as DataOps: “DataOps is a collaborative data management practice focused on improving the communication, integration, and automation of data flows between data managers and consumers across an organization. Much like DevOps, DataOps is not a rigid dogma, but a principles-based practice influencing how data can be provided and updated to meet the need of the organization’s data consumers. The goal of DataOps is to create predictable delivery and change management of data, data models and related artifacts. It uses technology to automate data delivery with the appropriate levels of security, quality, and metadata to improve the use and value of data in a dynamic environment.” [11]

Data preparation and semantic enrichment refer to the set of processes used to clean and transform the raw data prior to processing and analysis in the following stage. They involve detecting errors and making corrections to the data (e.g., removing outliers), combining data sets if needed, reformatting data, assigning (and standardizing) data formats, enriching source data, assigning a unified meaning (semantics) to the data, etc. These steps are not only needed for qualitative processing; they are also vital elements of data management that enable data governance. Especially when preparing data to be shared within an ecosystem of data pipeline actors, these steps are mandatory. The preparation and semantic enrichment need to be aligned to the domain challenges, and they must be conducted with consideration to their position in the data chain. As discussed in Section 4, bias in semantics is a significant risk. It is thus important to track semantic mappings and enrichment e.g., using knowledge graphs and information models and to offer these as metadata to the data pipeline clients.

Data mining and analysis refer to the set of processes that operate on prepared data sets and that search for and create patterns, trends, connections, aggregations, links, etc. The goal is to extract more value from the data, i.e., useful information that can be shared with the applications. This DataOps and InterOps focus also allows for data governance, so that the processed data can still be linked back to the raw data and its original meaning. This is important, for instance, when machine learning is used to detect clustering of data. The original raw data and its quality may change continuously, and new raw data sets may be added on the fly. Thus, while the flow of information may seem steady, its quality may change continuously. The concepts, explanations and ideas behind smart data are based on the details specified in [14], for a more thorough and elaborate deep-dive, we refer to the original whitepaper.

2.5. Digital Twin Reference Architecture

2.5.1. Conceptual architecture

The picture below is the conceptual architecture of the DUET [4] (Digital Urban European Twins) system. It is a conceptual architecture that illustrates that besides some key components that tie the different components together, the digital twin manifests itself as a distributed system of systems. This architecture brings challenges in terms of robustness, scalability and interoperability. In this section we discuss the architecture in terms of its different components.

Figure 9: The DUET T-Cell architecture [5] for interoperability

2.5.2. Data pipelines for Local Digital Twins

What makes out a local digital twin is the capability of combining both historic and live data with algorithms that can simulate and or predict real-life outcomes. The difficulty lies in a combination of requirements that typically coincide in responsive digital twins:

- (i) Bringing the data to the model
- (ii) Allowing the model to do its work in a fast, incremental (i.e., stream) fashion
- (iii) Showing the result on the screen relatively quickly to attain a responsive system

A large part of the answer is provided by Linked Data Event Streams (LDES) [7], a data streaming and replication protocol that allows data to be replicated in a way that minimizes the load on the source system by making maximal use of HTTP optimization such as caching. At the same time, the protocol is very simple and allows the client to stay synchronized as well.

The LDES approach ensures that models always have the latest data available when they need it while the role of the data publisher is limited to exactly what it should be limited to: to publish data, and not to maintain expensive scalable and available services for the benefit of many.

Figure 10: A vision for robust and responsive data pipelines as pushed forward by the Flemish Smart Data Space [13][14]. The LDES ecosystem, where the data publisher only serves HTTP cacheable data fragments with a specified retention period and where complex queries and heavy query load is diverted to services closer to the data user. The data service provider can always get in sync and stay in sync. After a disruption recovery is trivial.

LDES operates by tracking the full history of the data by capturing every version of every record as a data member. These members are grouped into fragments that – given the definitive nature of history – never change again. The fragments are referring to one another using the TREE hypermedia specification [8] to allow clients to discover the entire dataset from a single fragment. Using a plain HTTP server, these static fragments can be served very efficiently. Alongside, a stream of updates can also be published for the convenience of having shorter latency times than polling the last fragment for changes typically allows.

If data consumers wish to ask more complicated questions, they can use an LDES client to replicate the dataset in a local system that supports such queries. This takes away many requirements from the data publisher that can focus on maintaining the data set and focus on publishing data rather than supporting complex service infrastructure.

We propose to use LDES as an architectural pattern for event sourcing in Open Local Digital Twins.

2.5.3. Asset catalogue

An asset catalogue provides a descriptive overview of available datasets, schemas, vocabularies, algorithms and other usable building blocks. We discuss them in detail:

- **Datasets:** following the principles of Smart Data Management [14], any dataset used in a digital twin should be fully understood in terms of its trustworthiness and quality attributes. That means full insight into its lineage with sufficient trust towards integrity, but also a good description of the data and its quality so that its applicability for the intended use can be properly assessed. This full understanding implies that the dataset’s schema, format and semantics are clearly known.
- **Schema, format, vocabulary:** The asset catalog should be capable of listing available formats such that it can be assessed whether the form of the data is usable as it is. It should be equally capable of tracking the schemas of the data and their vocabularies (if applicable) in order to understand schematic and semantic compatibility with algorithms, processors and/or visualization tools.
- **Algorithms:** In order to use algorithms freely and combine them with data sets or compose them with other algorithms, it is helpful to also document the algorithms in terms of their data inputs and outputs. This allows to assess that an algorithm is indeed compatible with the data that a user intends to provide to it. Besides that, it is important to provide basic descriptions of algorithms and what can and cannot be expected of the algorithms in terms of quality and reliability for instance.
- **Other building blocks:** Besides algorithms such as simulation or machine learning models, other building blocks that are capable of transporting or transforming data can be made available as well.

The asset catalogue should rely on standards for asset metadata information sharing such as the DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary) and IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) information models and ontologies.

2.5.4. Knowledge graph

The knowledge graph is an optional component that can assist the asset catalog in categorizing assets such that the users can more easily find relevant assets for their cases.

The knowledge graph is based on open standards for linked data and combines the terms in the ontologies (see above) to make resources findable.

2.5.5. Message broker

The message broker facilitates the interplay between the models, the data sources and other parts of the digital twin by allowing messages to be sent between them. It allows to orchestrate the flow of data from data sources to models, between models and from models to other components such as the visualization client. Also, when a digital twin user interacts with the virtual environment, this leads to messages being relayed across the message broker so that other components can respond to it properly. This functionality is typically covered by a message streaming platform such as Kafka.

2.5.6. Interaction/orchestration service

The interaction or orchestration service fulfils the following roles:

- Interpreting the details of a scenario, as specified in the scenario manager and turn that into an abstract data flow that can be executed as intended,
- Starting, pausing, stopping a simulation from a scenario and storing of the simulation results,
- Allowing interactions to be seen as a source of data, to which the models can respond. A good example of such an interaction is the closing of a street where a model can detect the change and adjust traffic predicted flows.

2.5.7. Access Management

Access management is an important part of an open local digital twin. As we have pointed out earlier, these digital twins are designed to tackle complex challenges that typically involve multiple stakeholders by combining data and algorithms from many parties.

It should be possible to share data sources, models and even cases and scenarios in a controlled way such that not everyone that has access to the digital twin can access everything. This also allows to create market places where data, models and other tools can be offered against payment.

This calls for proper access management where identities can be validated using federated identity services and access control is organized independently from identity management using an ABAC (attribute-based access control) system [15]. As we will discuss later, this is a key principle of data spaces as well.

2.5.8. Case and Scenario Manager

As explained in section 2.2.5, case and scenario management enables structuring and managing the research that is done with digital twins. As such they fulfil a practical role, but they also have a technical part to play: they contain all the information that the interaction/orchestration service needs to properly run scenarios. They are an essential part of the abstraction that allows models and data sources of different vendors to be used in combination.

2.5.9. Digital twin management

A separate or integrated management module is needed for setting up the digital twin, onboard users, manage their access, etc. This module may also allow for instance

- Management of key users such as admins;
- Performing supportive actions, e.g., for locked accounts
- management of asset catalogue and its outside connectivity (i.e., for syncing with other catalogues)
- auditing/monitoring of other components such as the message broker
- registering 3rd party identity providers
- etc.

2.5.10. Visualization and the analytic environment

Visualization is often a key aspect of digital twins. Their capability of replicating an actual world system in a virtual environment and making that insightful often hinges on smart visualization that provides these insights.

There are different kinds of visualizations that can arguably be divided into the following categories:

- 2D/3D representations of the actual world. In the case of local digital twins, this is typically a map or a detail like an intersection. This enables visual confirmation to support the understanding of phenomena. The intended audience is typically end-users such as civilians, policy makers and other non-analytical-expert profiles.
- Charts and tables are typically used for a better analytical understanding such as pattern analysis, cluster analysis, ... These environments allow data scientists and other analytical experts to gain better insights into the different phenomena and their interdependence.

These two different environments need not be integrated but can co-exist independently. There can even be multiple of these environments each with its own purpose in mind. They are not core components either, but only connect through data endpoints with the digital twin.

2.5.11. Integrating data sources, algorithms and models

As explained earlier, we see great benefit from using LDES [7] as an interconnecting protocol for digital twins. Given that both data sources and algorithms may be offered as services and thus are not local to the DT installation, the challenge of building a robust and responsive twin increases greatly.

Figure 11 shows a typical scenario as it occurs in digital twins. Different models need data from external sources but may also rely on the outcome of another model. The latter is the case for an air quality model that uses traffic intensity to estimate pollution levels.

The approach of LDES to rely on replicating data and staying in sync allows to compose components without making many assumptions on:

- Responsiveness: the data resides locally to either the model or the twin client and responsiveness is easier to achieve that way
- Robustness: the LDES protocol ensures recoverability from outages

Figure 11 A typical data flow in digital twins where different data sources and models are interdependent and where LDES can be used as the universal glue between them.

An additional benefit is that in case one wants to support interactions where users of the digital twin can make changes in the virtual environment, then LDES can also be used to feed these changes back to the algorithms as changes or version objects of the manipulated object.

3. Dataspaces

3.1. What are data spaces?

3.1.1. From data exchange to data sharing

Data exchange is typically what happens when two companies in the logistics chain interact with each other. It can happen by exchanging data via email or other communication channels, or it can happen in fully automated ways using integrations. Data exchange is a necessity for logistics operations and can thus be considered a by-product of it.

 Data **exchange** in logistics can be defined as the act of exchanging data between two or more logistics parties for the sole purpose of completing one or more logistics tasks.

Figure 12 Data sharing is done without a specific process or interaction in mind. Data flows towards the entire ecosystem. This is different from the necessary data exchanges between the different logistics parties to facilitate the logistics processes.

Data sharing on the other hand is done without a specific purpose in mind. The idea is to share data for use by the logistics community, rather than just for the purpose of the logistics process. Data sharing in logistics is also not necessarily restricted to parties in the logistics chain. In order to clarify this we provide some examples:

- Shippers and consignees can decide to publish their transportation demand in a controlled and secure way in order to allow for cargo-sharing optimization in logistics,
- Transport service providers may be willing to share information that allows a trusted third party to find and propose cross-fleet transport optimizations,
- Trucking companies may be willing to share position data in order to track congestion for the better benefit of all transport service providers,
- Logistics operators may be willing to take part in the Physical Internet and publish their capabilities in a certain standard way,
- Weather service providers may offer weather predictions that can help to predict traffic congestion.

Data **sharing** in logistics can be defined as the act of securely publishing data and making it findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR principles) such that other parties can benefit from it. Data sharing includes data exchange but not the other way around.

Sharing data externally with partners can generate three times more economic benefits than not sharing data, according to a 2021 Gartner study. **One-to-one integration**, or point-to-point integration, is a basic way of exchanging data that involves a middleware or software that facilitates data transformation and transport between two systems. However, it has serious shortcomings such as a lack of scalability, inflated security risk, and costly maintenance.

Hub-and-spoke integration is an alternative to one-to-one integration that uses a central hub to connect systems seeking to communicate data. This approach simplifies matters from an architectural, security, and sustainability standpoint, but still has a single party responsible for various tasks related to the central hub.

Alternatively, a **data space** can be defined, where data is shared peer-to-peer among digital services with individuals' consent and fair value redistribution, adhering to agreed-on standards on both technical interoperability and business practices. This approach allows for more control over data exchange rules and distribution. The publisher remains in control and there is no one party that can exploit the fact of controlling all the data.

3.1.2. The challenges of data sharing

Data sharing has become increasingly important in today's digital age, but it also poses a number of challenges:

- One of the challenges is that data platforms, which are often used for integration, can be a new problem for many users who are unfamiliar with them and need to integrate with them.

- Additionally, publishers have no control over what happens to their data once it is shared, and users have no way of knowing how trustworthy the data is. This highlights the need for sovereignty and control over data.
- Another challenge is that data can be difficult to find, as there are often no standardized metadata or vocabulary providers, making it hard for users to discover the right data for their needs.
- Trust also needs to be established bilaterally between data publishers and users, requiring an identity provider and governance structure.
- In addition, there are no structural ways to track data usage from a policy or remuneration perspective, which further highlights the need for a decentralized network of data publishers acting on behalf of data owners.

This network, known as data spaces, can bridge gaps between data platforms and existing publishing tools and infrastructure by creating a more open, decentralized system of data sharing.

Overall, data sharing presents several challenges that need to be addressed, including issues of control, trust, findability, and tracking. However, data spaces offer a potential solution to these challenges by creating a more decentralized and open network of data publishers that can act on behalf of data owners.

3.1.3. A definition of dataspace

A dataspace is defined as a decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles.

More elaborately, data spaces can be defined as decentralized, secure, and interoperable environments where data can be shared and accessed by different parties in a trusted and controlled manner. They aim to bridge the gaps between different data platforms and tools, enabling a network of data publishers to act on behalf of data owners and facilitating data exchange based on agreed standards and protocols. Data spaces provide a foundation for developing data-driven business models and services, while also ensuring privacy, security, and sovereignty over data.

3.2. Dataspace reference architecture

3.2.1. Key aspects and Design Principles of Data Spaces

The key aspects and principles are based on technical, legal, business and governance fundamentals. The DSSC **Error! Reference source not found.** checklist for data spaces gives a good overview which key aspects need to be taken into consideration. The checklist is listed in **Figure 1413**.

Data Spaces Start-up Checklist

Business: Value and Models

- How does the data space create value?
- Who creates value, and for whom is value generated?
- What is the business and governance model of the data space?
- What are the individual and collaborative business models (Incentives) for the actors in the data space?
- What is the data and organizational governance model?

Legal and Governance

- What legal aspects are relevant to navigate when setting up a data space?
- How can data spaces ensure the full uptake of EU values?

Operational

- What is the operational governance framework for the data space?
- Who are the active stakeholders or participants of the data space?
- How will you assure and gain trust from data holders and users?

Functionality

- What are the essential technical services you need to implement in your data space?
- Are there existing dependencies?
- What are the data standards you will use to ensure interoperability between partners in your data space and in other data spaces?

Technology

- What technology stacks (e.g., open source implementations, standard specifications) will you use to create or join a data space?

DATA SPACES SUPPORT CENTRE

Figure 1413: checklist as proposed by the DSSC

As can be seen in the checklist, there are different aspects to be considered, leading to dataspace that can consolidate and instantiate them using specific domain criteria. Within different domains or sectors, a lot of legacy business, legal, operational, technical agreements have been made already, and need to be lifted to a governance level possibly fused with emerging enablers, such as GAIA-X compliant services (e.g., iShare) and IDS compliant connectors and components (e.g. the Eclipse Dataspace connector). Examples on regulation level are the upcoming European acts such as the Data Act, Data Governance Act, AI Act, ... but also with upcoming technical elements such as linked data standards. More information on the checklist can be consulted at the DSSC website [17].

In that sense, a dataspace setup needs to consider the different aspects that are summarized in **Figure 15: 14**. This figure gives an overview on the crucial technical and governance building blocks for data spaces [18].

KEY ASPECTS OF A DATA SPACE

Figure 15: 14 Design principles for Data Spaces [18]

As we can see, dataspace are leveraged to enable interoperability, trust and value, and need governance to make it happen. That is why dataspace are key to realize data sharing at large or societal scale and cannot be instantiated just by one or a few parties. The different building blocks all need to be addressed to make data space a reality. Detailed descriptions of the building blocks can be found in the relevant OpenDei and IDSA documentations. We will make it more concrete by describing how the data pipeline we described in 3.4.2 and its encompassing VSIDS program (Vlaamse Smart Data Space) can be a reference example on how to implement the different building blocks, together with building blocks identified by the IDSA.

Data Models & Formats: Data sharing starts with formal descriptions of the meaning of the data, models to express that and profiles to apply. There are different official places to get the inspiration from: international organizations and initiatives such as schema.org, W3C, Fiware smart data models but also local translations such as OSLO (<https://data.vlaanderen.be/standaarden/>) that map different official standards and vocabularies into e.g., linked data application profiles. A dataspace needs to govern the use of these data models & formats, as the descriptions of the data are crucial in being able to discover the data from a metadata broker. There can be multiple vocabularies provided (see IDSA vocabulary provider in 3.2.2) but they need to be registered and managed. Within the LDES pipeline, there are also descriptions in Linked Data Formats to express the protocol to communicate (e.g., to link fragments together).

Data Exchange APIs: The LDES pipeline clearly offers standardized APIs to exchange (publish, consume...) data and metadata considering especially scalability concerns and balance between data

providers and data consumers in setting up IT infrastructure. Moreover, it stimulates intermediate service providers (see again the functional role description in 3.2.2) to contribute to a healthy data sharing landscape.

Provenance & Traceability: Having well established and defined data models, formats and data exchange APIs makes it possible to implement provenance, lineage and traceability. Again, to give an example on the data exchange API's using LDES, an example is described in the paper published on <https://biblio.ugent.be/publication/8771000/file/8771003.pdf>. This paper describes the Smart Data Specification for Semantically Describing Streams (SDS) to annotate dataset interfaces with provenance information, describing the consumed stream and the applied transformations on that stream.

Identity Management: Being able to uniquely and trustworthily identify participants of the dataspace is key to enabling the trust and sovereignty. For example with Linked Data Event Streams using the decentralized web protocols, WebIDs can be used together with well-established standards like OpenID Connect and OAuth2.0.

Access & Usage Control/policies: The IDSA has standardised information models with templates for usage policies, augmenting the contract definitions embedded in dataspace connectors. Of course, these usage policies need to be traced and/or enforced, as much as possible from a technical perspective. Access policies can be implemented in different ways. As an example with LDES streams, derived streams could be setup in function of persona rights.

Trusted Exchange: Identity management and access/usage policies are important elements in establishing trust & sovereignty. However, other elements can be needed to establish trust, like certification, remote attestation, or even transaction logging maintained by a clearing house (see 3.2.2)

Metadata & Discovery Protocol: The OpenDei design principles promote in this context the sharing of metadata using semantic web technologies and linked-data principles. That is also the base of the VSIDS project using web and linked data standards in all of its flavours. Enabling trust starts with metadata management based on official vocabularies. In that context, LDES can also be used to publish metadata with full time travel and versioning to also track changes in the metadata, that are key to the evolution of the ecosystem of the dataspace (see component "broker" in 3.2.2).

Data Usage Accounting: Road blocks for sharing data are not only the trust in its use and destination, but also the costs that need to be made to share the data. LDES takes this into account by only sharing data updates, this way providing a better controllable cost sharing between producers and consumers. In addition, components such as clearing houses (see 3.2.2) can add the necessary infrastructure to accounting access and implementing transaction attributes (e.g. billing) on data sharing events taking place. This is needed to enable healthy marketplaces where also new business service providers can implement healthy business models.

Publication & marketplace services: The presence of the above building blocks is needed to eventually build marketplaces. Defining smart contracts, leveraging them to a verifiable level, attaching payment models, new service provider services on data (hosting, transformation, storing, refining, ...) are all part of marketplace services and will need marketplace components (e.g. supporting smart contracts).

An important aspect of a dataspace is the governance. In order to have some level of trust, partakers in the ecosystem must be identified, so governance over identities is important. Equally important is the governance on the use of standards. This concerns is described in the OpenDei white paper and out of scope of this section.

3.2.2. Functional Reference architecture

The functional reference architecture for data sharing within dataspaces is defined by IDSA (see **Figure 15**) in the RAM (Reference Architecture Model), which is currently in its official version 3.0 but version 4.0 is in review stage. The different roles and building blocks are described in the figure below and are already referred to where applicable in section 4.2.1.

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Figure 15: The functional Reference Architecture Model for sharing data within dataspaces by IDSA

The description of the different actors in this system, can be found within the IDSA documentation portal (<https://internationaldataspaces.org/use/ids-components/>) and will not be repeated here. To

realize a minimum dataspace that can connect multiple stakeholders to each other within any project, following elements are key:

- Definition of a connector that fits the purpose and allows basic agreed upon communication methods with the basic components like the metadata broker, another connector, and the identity provider
- An agreed upon vocabulary provider (or providers) so that connectors that offer access to certain datasets can be found systematically (as multiple providers can offer datasets of the same kind)
- If trust needs to be expressed in terms of establishing access to certain identities, then an identity provider is mandatory together with the components to enable trust (Certification Authority, ...)
- Other components are applicable when needed.

3.3. Relevance for digital twins

Open Local Digital Twins are digital representations of physical assets, systems, or environments, created by combining data from various sources such as sensors, IoT devices, and other digital systems. They allow stakeholders to visualize and simulate real-world scenarios, test potential solutions, and improve decision-making processes. However, the success of Open Local Digital Twins relies heavily on the availability and quality of data and services from different stakeholders, such as local authorities, businesses, and citizens.

To address the challenges of data sharing and collaboration in Open Local Digital Twins, data space aspects can be applied. Firstly, discoverability is crucial for stakeholders to identify and access relevant data and services. Data spaces enable metadata management and search functionality to improve discoverability and facilitate data exchange.

Secondly, trust is essential for stakeholders to feel confident in sharing and using data. Data spaces provide a framework for establishing trust relationships and enforcing data governance and security policies.

Thirdly, interoperability ensures that data can be exchanged and combined seamlessly between different systems and platforms. Data spaces provide standardized data models, interfaces, and protocols to improve interoperability and reduce the costs and complexity of data integration.

Fourthly, decentralized identity and access management enable stakeholders to control access to their data and services and protect their privacy. Data spaces provide mechanisms for secure authentication, authorization, and delegation of access rights.

Finally, data sovereignty ensures that data owners have control over their data and how it is used. Data spaces provide mechanisms for tracking data provenance, usage, and compliance with legal and ethical frameworks, ensuring that data is used in a justified and accountable manner.

Overall, applying data space aspects to Open Local Digital Twins can improve collaboration, innovation, and value creation for stakeholders, while also ensuring privacy, security, and compliance with legal and ethical standards.

Trust in the context of this project also involves the limitations that apply to sharing data for inland waterways. As inland Waterway Vessels are often also the home of their shippers, tracking them can incur concerns regarding privacy. Other restrictions may apply to different datasets as well.

Dataspaces can make these restrictions explicit through policies that apply to the datasets and that are reflected in the agreements used to initiate data transfer.

In the last chapter of this document, we explore how the digital twin reference architecture discussed in 2.5 can be mapped onto the data space reference architecture in 3.2.2.

4. Digital Twins as Dataspace Apps

4.1. Mapping the ODT architecture onto dataspaces

Dataspaces as discussed in chapter 4 are fundamental for the scalable deployment of digital twins as we discussed in our DUET architecture in chapter 3. This was pitched in [19] and recently confirmed in [20]. From the last paper we quote : *"We argue that it is the combination of the concept of dataspaces and digital twins that enables one to realize the original idea of a digital twin as a comprehensive virtual representation of a physical asset."*

4.2. Digital Twin Components and Dataspaces

4.2.1. Facilitating DT data flows across dataspace connectors

Data can be delivered to a digital twin and its components in many ways. The open local digital twin (OLDT) architecture explicitly abstracts from data transfer protocols as it recognizes that the appropriate way of sharing data can be dependent on the specific application. Here, an interesting observation applies to the data space architecture as it is proposed by IDSA.

The IDS architectural description and the diagrams [21] indicate that a dataspace connector acts as an intermediary between the data user and the data publisher. They allow to negotiate an agreement between the data publisher and the data user prior to the actual data transfer. Upon a request, a session can be established that is shorter lived than the agreement itself.

The session information can be used by client applications to establish direct connections with the data services. This pattern can help ensure efficient data transfer using diverse protocols. Understanding the dynamics between digital twins and data spaces at this level is considered part of this work package.

Figure 16: Aside from just the dataflows, dataspace bring added value in terms of data discovery, agreements and tracking usage of data.

4.2.2. Inbound and Outbound Data

In order to consume data from data spaces as well as to publish data to a data space, the digital twin will need to have a fully-fledged data space connector. This allows to have dataspace compliant identity & rights management, negotiation of agreements and validation of protocols, etc. This implies among other things that the digital twin is capable of the following:

- integrating with trusted identity providers in the IDSA dataspace
- providing access control in line with IDSA dataspace deployment where attributes can be managed in the dataspace
- mapping metadata to and from the IDSA data model

4.2.3. Models

Open Local Digital Twins are by design intended to freely (re)use data and models provided with or without profit by other parties. They can occur either as locally deployed assets or as services that are deployed remotely (SaaS, i.e., software-as-a-service). To transpose that model to dataspaces is an interesting exercise. Not only does it mean that a connector should be able to allow the use of non-data services, but it also means that these services, when deployed remotely will need to access data in the name of the digital twin user. Data spaces and their connector architecture are suitable for both deployment patterns.

4.2.4. Digital twin core components

The management components and UI (user interfaces) are typically deployed together with the metadata catalogue, the case & scenario manager and the interaction & orchestration service. They share a common dataspace connector that acts as middleware to connect with the outside dataspace world. Essentially this means from the perspective of the T-Cell conceptual architecture that a dataspace connector is a specific kind of receptor on the Open Local Digital Twin.

4.3. The big picture

Putting things together, a digital twin and some of its components deployed in a dataspace could look as in **Figure 17**.

Figure 17: A sketch of the dataspace deployment of an Open Local Digital Twin

All parties of the digital twin expose a dataspace connector for making their data/services available. This automatically adds a layer on top of a basic Open Local Digital Twin deployment, bringing added value to the Digital Twin in the form of data discovery, data usage policies, sovereign identity management, increased interoperability, etc.

This big picture is about the end-to-end dataflows in the context of digital twins. It is well-established that the principles of smart data need to be applied end-to-end as well in order to come to useful solutions.

This implies that the data provider applies all of the principles of data governance and that all aspects of smart data are published transparently through the data space connectors. This includes information about the technical nature of the data but also about the quality, the lineage, etc.

Zooming in on the data exchange from and to the digital twin (see **Figure 16**), we notice a few things:

- The IDS connector may act as a way for the digital twin to discover new potentially interesting data sources. At the same time, it enables third parties to publish their data in a trustworthy way, taking away some of the reluctance to share it openly.
- The IDS connector mainly takes care of the trust facet of the exchange. In many drawings that can be found on dataspaces, the data flow is often depicted to pass through the connector. This can make sense in some cases but for the sake of building robust and responsive digital twins, this is not desirable. The connector will allow to open a session and using a session token, the data can be retrieved from the data source directly.

Figure 18: The flow of control from the twin to the model does not pass through the connectors

The control flow from the digital twin’s orchestration engine to the model follows a similar itinerary: Once the model is discovered and the API endpoint is known, the connector is used for establishing trust up until the point that a session is created. A session token can then be used to call the model API directly.

5. Conclusion

The ongoing refinement of the different Living Labs is preventing us from mapping the architecture onto the use cases in the living labs in a very detailed fashion. Nevertheless, we propose an architecture that touches on the key goals of the work package as specified in the compliance table at the beginning of this deliverable.

More specifically, the key contributions of this deliverable are as follows:

- We propose a generic architecture for digital twins inspired by the experiences and proven solutions developed in DUET and other digital twin projects;
- We explain the valuable role that data spaces can play in connection data and algorithms to the digital twin;
- We present a design pattern for data interactions based on the SEMIC specification Linked Data Event Streams (LDES) with the following value proposition
 - Built-in data time travel capability,
 - Accommodates the use of linked data and open standards, including Fiware, OSLO and OGC standards,
 - Robust data transfer that can recover from interruptions,
 - Scalable data publishing through a minimal API,
 - Flexible data publishing that allows to consume the data in multiple formats and services,
 - TRL-9 components for deployment (i.e. building blocks that are considered to be matured and ready for practical applications in real-world settings)
- The combined architecture is a blueprint for data-supported decision making and is the foundation of the IWT-specific solution accelerator that we envision to create.

We posit that this architecture and the underpinning principles will sufficiently support the use cases. Furthermore, as a generic approach towards integrating dataspace and digital twins, it supports the creation of Asset 3: Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT) Dataspace and generic Digital Twin directly and the other assets indirectly.

Finally, a roadmap for the realization of this architecture depends on the use cases from the LivingLabs that require further refinement. In the appendix 2 we describe the first high-level user stories from the LivingLabs.

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Appendix I Digital Twin Capabilities

Selecting digital twin capabilities

As we have identified in previous chapters, a digital twin at scale is a complex ecosystem where different capabilities are needed to address its use cases. When building digital twins at scale, focusing on assembling the right technological capabilities together is also the strategy that is proposed by the Digital Twin Consortium. This Consortium has summarized these capabilities within a digital twin Periodic Table (see **Figure 20**). In the next paragraph, we will shortly introduce this table.

Capabilities Framework as identified by the Digital Twin Consortium

The periodic table analogy is highly useful to organise the capabilities of any system. It refers to the analogy with the (chemical) periodic table of elements and is not just a collection of elements, but it has a fixed structure that follows a certain logic. First, these capabilities are organized into Categories, as depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Figure 19: Categories of digital twin capabilities: summary figure taken from [3]

Figure 20: Detailed capabilities: summary figure taken from [3]

Aligning with this periodic table of technology-based capabilities provides a categorisation that is agnostic to specific technology or product solutions. This allows one to compose digital twins in function of the ambition levels (see **Figure 2**) that are defined upfront (e.g., in ReNEW living labs).

In our reference architecture, we focus mainly on these capabilities that address the Gemini principles, and thus also assist in the creation of a Web of Twins. In the next paragraphs, we focus on these capabilities.

Capabilities addressing the PURPOSE principles

We refer to **Figure 1** and the related Gemini principles, purpose, trust & function. The purpose of a local digital twin is to create value for the public good. This must be done by maximizing on the insights, not only in the built environment, but also in the digital environment that is used. ReNEW uses digital twins to have better insights into the built environment of the critical infrastructure, but also aims at performance improvements by addressing impact of mitigation scenarios on attack events.

Different components can be used to increase the User Experience using digital twins. Increasing the user experience (UX) will contribute largely to the purpose of the digital twin: it will enhance the insights and assist the decision-making process for operational and disaster managers using the digital twin. In this way, the different digital assets and engines used are made more explicit and converge their power towards the users of the digital twin.

Also, in the digital twin periodic table, the UX is a category on its own, containing capabilities such as visualisations, dashboarding, business and continuous intelligence, workflow engines, gaming engine visualization, gamification, AR & VR (augmented & virtual reality).

Capabilities addressing the TRUST principles

The second principle mentioned in **Figure 1** and the related Gemini principles is Trust. This is a very important principle when designing a digital twin for the public good and purpose. Local digital twins are mostly cross-domain of nature, and in ReNEW, this is a mandatory feature as the goal is to assess the environmental & resilience effects within the living labs on IWT. Having trust in the use of multiple cross-domain datasets and simulation engines does not come for free and needs to be addressed by implementation of multiple capabilities.

Quality, Openness and Security are very important sub-principles of TRUST. We have referred to smart data (and smart assets) in section **2.4** before and consider the capabilities to address this “smartness” as key enablers for building trust in complex digital twin compositions. Also, in the Periodic Table, “trustworthiness” is a specific category and addressed by capabilities such as data encryption, security, safety, device security, privacy, reliability, and resilience of the underlying digital twin system itself. In that context, we refer to section **2.3** where we introduced resilient and cognitive digital twins.

In our reference architecture, we focus mostly on a Web of Twins approach, connecting multiple digital twins together to possibly multiple data spaces. For that, our focus lies on enabling capabilities that are assisting expression and tracing of quality of data, qualitative use of the data within digital twin scenarios to support the insight and openness using semantics of data and simulation models. In this sense, enabling trust also needs the right management and data service capabilities, like data governance, ontology management, simulation model repositories, etc.

The following capabilities are not an exhaustive list, but advise a selection of capabilities that can support the ReNEW requirements in some of the living labs:

- **Data Type capabilities (supporting semantics):** It is very important to be able to unify the different semantics of contributing assets and make them explicit, from a business and technical perspective. From the periodic table, data management capabilities like ontology management, contextualization, repositories for digital twins and simulation models, data stores, ... are essential enablers. Data storage, lineage, collection, mapping, querying, projections, and so forth, all also need to be enabled for “type or semantic” level metadata.
- **Data Value capabilities (supporting big data):** digital twins consume large amounts of data, but also produce a lot of data. Having reliable Lambda or Kappa architectures in place to support big data is crucial. Lambda Architecture is a data processing approach that combines batch processing and real-time/stream processing to handle large volumes of data. It uses separate paths for batch and real-time data processing, allowing for scalability, fault tolerance, and flexibility in handling different types of data. This architecture is useful when dealing with

big data scenarios that require both batch processing for large-scale data analytics and real-time/stream processing for low-latency data processing and quick insights. Kappa Architecture, on the other hand, is a streamlined approach that simplifies the data processing pipeline by using only real-time/stream processing for all data. It eliminates the need for separate batch processing and simplifies the data pipeline, making it easier to manage and maintain. This architecture is particularly useful when dealing with data streams that require real-time processing, such as in IoT (Internet of Things) applications, where data is generated continuously and needs to be processed in near real-time for timely insights and actions. The focus on real-time processing comes at a cost, being that batch processing is left to be implemented as if it was a stream. It is key to be able to combine efficiently Data Semantics/Types and Data Values together into either one of these architectures. It is also very important to be able to address continuous quality validations for data value and data type level transactions and changes within the architecture.

- **Data Intelligence/transformation capabilities:** in digital twins, data is continuously being enriched, transformed, projected, queried, scraped, etc. Simulation models in “What If” enabled Level 4 digital twins (see **Figure 2**) use data, transform it (feature engineering) and create new data with more value. We need to apply data type and value capabilities, and this requires new capabilities like model management, model signatures, compute lineage, etc. Also, important quality metrics (like expressing the quality metrics such as the accuracy of AI models need to be managed. AI models are continuously being re-trained, and thus the lineage of quality is also subject to change constantly. The capability to track the provenance of these changes is essential to be able to compare different analysis sessions within digital twins to each other and is a base for building wisdom within different scenarios or simulations in ReNEW.
- **Integration capabilities:** offer the means to couple trust capabilities like metadata stores to UX level capabilities like asset inventories that deliver the insights toward the domain stakeholders. Orchestration and integration capabilities are key (see integration category of the periodic table). Examples are integrations between the scenario managers and inventories @ UX level with real deployment of digital assets in the smart data federated platform.

Capabilities addressing the FUNCTION principles

The third principles mentioned in **Figure 1** and the related Gemini principles is function. To be able to make a digital twin implementation function in a scalable and durable way, federation, curation and being ready for evolutions are key principles. Especially in complex systems of systems such as ReNEW, which are targeting complex relationships and using cross-domain digital computation and data assets, the digital twins should ensure a scalable and future-proof interworking. For that, the data platform should be federated by nature, and thus allow standardized connectivity and orchestration. Moreover, allowing governance of the system is key to be able to keep on trusting the results and associated knowledge as summarized in the knowledge graphs. Knowledge graphs need to be continuously “connected” to the assets that contribute to this knowledge. Moreover, it is

important to avoid technical lock-in in making choices to implement the capabilities, as lock-in would hinder quick adoption of new technologies that contribute to the digital twin purpose.

When targeting important smart data and digital twin requirements as security and privacy (or data protection), it must be always considered in a federated, distributed system. The setup must allow for data to move to the location where the processing happens & the compute power is located (e.g., servers of another entity). However, the reversed use case should also be achievable, where compute (e.g., the algorithm or computation) physically moves the data (e.g., in case the dataset is too big to send over the internet). Both scenarios should be compliant to the security and privacy requirements with regards to algorithms and the data itself. For this, orchestration within a federated system is a key capability that addresses a Web of Twins to be connected. Several European projects (e.g., DUET [4]) and initiatives (e.g., Living-in.eu [1]) are targeting future standardization of these capabilities. In the meantime, it is possible to make implementation choices that come very close to a modular realization and thus future standardization.

The major FUNCTION principles that could contribute to a digital twin within ReNEW:

- **Federation/ Distribution of the data and compute assets** contributing to the TRUST principles. Distributed storage, federated metadata sharing and DT model building, trusted sandboxes for AI model training, federated data catalogues, ... are examples of sub-capabilities that contribute to this capability and link up to the concept of data spaces.
- **Orchestration that supports federation and distribution in its core.** It is clear that orchestration and federation not only need standards for connectivity and metadata but also need to find ways to unify orchestration of these assets being available on various providers within a data space.

Appendix II High-level backlog definition

Based on workshops and multiple interactions with the LivingLab leaders within ReNEW as well as with contributors to Work Package 1, 2 and 4, we have outlined for each LivingLab a preliminary backlog in which we state epics and user stories.

This backlog is considered as a dynamic work instrument that by time will be adapted according to among others data access constraints, pivoting ambitions of the LivingLab-leaders or more refined KPI (key performance indicators) setting and alignment requirements from Work Package 1. As such the backlog as described below is a snapshot of how WP3 perceives the epics and user stories at the time this deliverable was published.

For some of the LivingLabs this implies that we foresee a Digital Twin at ambition level 3 with a focus on situational awareness. For other LivingLabs ambition level 4 may be reached, including simulations and what-if scenarios (as described by **Figure 2**).

LivingLab 1

LivingLab Epic	User Story	Priority (High, Medium, Low)	High Level Estimate (in MD)
LL1	General Setup As an administrator I want to have basic user management so only people with the right login can access the app
LL1	General Setup As a user I want to have a map overview of the Client area with basic map controls (zoom, pan, 3D-toggle, street names, search)
LL1	Floating Modular Platform As a user I want to track the positioning of the FMP on the map in (nearly) real-time
LL1	Floating Modular Platform As a user I want to view a pop-up with AIS detail from the FMP upon clicking on the vessel (FMP-pop-up)
LL1	Floating Modular Platform As a user I want to click on a button in the FMP-pop-up that redirects me to the remote control environment of the FMP (external website)
LL1	Battery Tab As a user I want to view the current battery level of the FMP battery pack in a separate battery tab of the FMP-pop-up
LL1	Battery Tab As a user I want to view the historic battery level of the FMP battery pack in a separate battery tab of the FMP-pop-up
LL1	Battery Tab As a user I want to view the extra metadata of the FMP battery pack in a separate battery tab of the FMP-pop-up
LL1	Sensor Dashboard Tab As a user I want to view the last 24h of all sensor readings per spill pollutant as a line chart in a separate sensor tab of the FMP-pop-up
LL1	Smart City Terminal As a user I want to view a pop-up with detailed info from the SCT upon clicking on the building (SCT-Pop-up)
LL1	Smart City Terminal As a user I want to view weekly outbound logistics planning in a separate tab in the SCT-Pop-up as calendar visual
LL1	Smart City Terminal As a user I want to view weekly inbound logistics planning in a separate tab in the SCT-Pop-up on a calendar visual
LL1	Remote Controlled Crane As a user I want to view a pop-up with detailed info from the crane upon clicking on the building (crane-pop-up)
LL1	Remote Controlled Crane As a user I want to view whether the crane is currently being operated in the crane-pop-up as a green/red light
LL1	Remote Controlled Crane As a user I want to view other relevant metadata in the crane-pop-up
LL1	Drone As a user I want to click on a button in the crane-pop-up that redirects me to the remote control environment of the crane (external website)
LL1	Drone As a user I want to be able to track the location of the remote controlled drone
LL1	Drone As a user I want to view a pop-up with detail from the drone upon clicking on the drone (drone-pop-up)
LL1	Drone As a user I want to click on a button in the drone-pop-up that redirects me to the remote control environment of the drone (external website)
LL1	Inbound Logistics As a user I want to track the positioning of incoming vessels, coming to drop off goods at the SCT in (nearly) real-time
LL1	Inbound Logistics As a user I want to view a pop-up with detail from incoming vessel upon clicking on the drone
LL1	Inbound Logistics As a user I want to see whether vessels are platooning & if so, which vessels are grouped together (with their respective data in a popup)
LL1	Outbound Logistics As a user I want to track the positioning of outbound vehicles, coming to pick-up goods at the SCT in (nearly) real-time
LL1	Outbound Logistics As a user I want to view a pop-up with detail from the incoming vehicle upon clicking on the drone
Remarks These topics are needed for each of the datasets mentioned above & could be put in each epic			
Onboarding dataset X			
Data processing of dataset X			
Publishing dataset X			
Remark All these epics require the availability of the relevant datasets through an API or some sort of integration			
Remark Prioritisation to be done together with LL1 & WP1 / WP3			
Remark Estimation & work distribution amongst partners to be discussed			

LivingLab 2

LivingLab Epic	User Story	Priority (High, Medium, Low)	High Level Estimate (in MD)
Flooding Case			
LL2	Water Levels	As a user want to visualise the locations where water level measurements happen as dots on a map	...
LL2	Water Levels	As a user want to visualise the current water levels (in real time) by colouring the various locations (e.g. dark blue = high, red = low)	...
LL2	Water Levels	As a user want to visualise the historical water levels of a measuring location in a pop-up & as linelchart, upon clicking on a certain location	...
LL2	Weather Forecast	As a user want to visualise the current weather forecast on a map	...
LL2	Weather Forecast	As a user want to visualise the weather forecast for the upcoming 3h on a map	...
LL2	Flooding Model	As a user want to visualise the results of the flooding model (for the current time) on a map & highlight zones that have high flooding risks	...
LL2	Flooding Model	As a user want to visualise the results of the flooding model (for the coming 3h) on a map & highlight zones that have high flooding risks	...
LL2	Scenario Builder	As a user want to manually input hypothetical water levels at certain locations as input to the model	...
LL2	Scenario Builder	As a user want to manually input hypothetical weather forecasts at certain locations as input to the model	...
LL2	Scenario Builder	As a user want to save these hypothetical parameters as a scenario & give it a name	...
LL2	Scenario Builder	As a user want to run the flooding model with a created scenario & visualize the result on the map	...
Waste Water Case			
LL2	AIS Positioning	As a user want to see the position of the currently active vessels on the Douro river	...
LL2	AIS Positioning	As a user want to see the historical positions of vessels on the Douro river	...
LL2	AIS Positioning	As a user want to see available metadata in a pop-up when clicking on a given vessel	...
LL2	Waste Water Levels	As a user want to see the historical waste water levels of a selected barge as a linelchart	...
LL2	Disposal Zones	As a user want to see the zones of the Douro river where disposal of wastewater is allowed	...
LL2	Rule Engine	As a user want to have an overview of all historical (illegal) waste water disposals in a list	...
LL2	Rule Engine	As a user want to get an alert when an illegal waste water disposal happened	...
Remarks These topics are needed for each of the datasets mentioned above & could be put in each epic			
Onboarding dataset X			
Data processing of dataset X			
Publishing dataset X			
Remark All these epics require the availability of the relevant datasets through an API or some sort of integration			
Remark Prioritisation to be done together with LL2 & WPI / WPI3			
Remark Estimation & work distribution amongst partners to be discussed			

LivingLab 3

LivingLab Epic	User Story	Priority (High, Medi, High Level Estimate (in MD)
LL3	Static Terminal planner As a terminal, I would like to have an agenda module so that I can better plan my operations
LL3	Static Terminal planner As a terminal, I would like to get an overview of how many vessels are currently being handled, are waiting and will arrive
LL3	Static Terminal planner As a terminal, I would like to have an estimation of the vessel handling time (based on cargo, vessel type, ...)
LL3	Static Terminal planner As a terminal, I would like a booking module to allocate a timeslot to an incoming vessel
LL3	Realtime ETA As a terminal I want to know the (realtime) estimated time of arrival of incoming vessels
LL3	Dynamic terminal planner As a terminal, I want to update AND optimise the terminal planner based on deviating realtime ETAs of incoming vessels
LL3	Dynamic terminal planner As a terminal I want to simulate the cascading impact of changing ETA and ETD on the static terminal planner
LL3	Skipper feedback As a skipper I want to know when my ship is planned to be (un)loaded at the terminal based on the terminal planner
LL3	Skipper feedback As a skipper I want to get an update on the planning of the (un)loading at the terminal of my ship when the planning changes
LL3	Skipper feedback As a skipper I want to receive an update on optimised vessel speed to the terminal based on the dynamic terminal planner
LL3	RENEW objectives As a researcher I want to know how much emissions (CO2 / NO2) vessels incoming to the terminal emit
LL3	RENEW objectives As a researcher I want to simulate the impact on emissions if barges optimize their speed to the terminal according to the Skipper feedback
LL3	
Remarks	These topics are needed for each of the datasets mentioned above & could be put in each epic	
	Onboarding dataset X	
	Data processing of dataset X	
	Publishing dataset X	
Remark	All these epics require the availability of the relevant datasets through an API or some sort of integration	
Remark	Prioritisation to be done together with LL2 & WPI / WPI3	
Remark	Estimation & work distribution amongst partners to be discussed	

